

EDITORIAL

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Emerging Environmental Contaminants: Need for Mitigation Strategies

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*Correspondence for materials should be addressed to JS (email: jpsrattan@rediffmail.com)**Abstract**

Emerging Environmental Contaminants (EECs) are industrial effluents that poses risks to ecological integrity throughout the globe as these are the significant contributors of environmental pollution. According to United States Geological Survey (USGS) - any chemical or microorganism (synthetic or natural) not under regular surveillance, suspected for adverse human or ecological effects is considered as Emerging Environmental Contaminant (EEC). Apart from environment issues, these EECs that includes wide array of micropollutants also have serious concerns towards human health. Equally known as Emerging pollutants (EPs), these EECs include perfluorinated compounds, human and veterinary pharmaceuticals, fire retardants, gasoline additives, UV filters, manufactured nanoparticles, synthetic fragrances, personal care products, disinfectants, microplastics and preservatives etc. EECs contaminate all the three abiotic components i.e. air, water and soil; therefore, are potentially harmful for microorganisms, plants as well as animals (biotic components) in the biosphere. The diverse groups comprising EECs are unregulated, thereby are increasingly accumulating in the environment. These EECs are continuously challenging the agricultural ecosystem by way of the abiotic as well as biotic stresses. These anthropogenically generated compounds are accumulative in nature leading to both soil as well as water bodies pollution. In recent years, the climate change due to accumulative EECs has led to disturbed ecosystems at different zones of the globe posing numerous challenges to food for human wellbeing and forage for domestic animals. The challenges offered by EECs towards their control measures include lack of perception, misapprehension, scarcity of scientific investigations and explorations for their occurrence, estimations, intensification as the most common hurdles to researcher in unravelling the strategies that may cope these EECs.

Keywords: Emerging Contaminants; Industrialization; Industrial effluents; Biosphere**Introduction**

Industrial revolution in 21st century that leads to the production of numerous novel chemicals coined the concept of Emerging Environmental Contaminants (EECs). Emphasis on these potential environmental contaminants (Kaur et al., 2023; Riaz et al., 2023; Abarna and Sathya, 2025; Langat et al., 2024) gained momentum by the invention and further evolution of advanced analytical techniques facilitating the detection of these EECs at lower levels, i.e. even microgram concentrations. Depending upon the origin, usage and physicochemical characterisation investigated by analytical techniques, the EECs are classified into various categories. Environmental persistence, extensive public health impact, bioaccumulation tendency as well as unknown risks are the major issues to be addressed by research and development on EECs. along with further lay outing of their management strategies (Li et al., 2024).

Modernization practices leading to industrialization and urbanization have resulted in increased EECs viz. municipal wastewaters. The industrial effluents adding EECs in the surface as well as groundwaters are ultimately polluting the natural sources of drinking water. In a way, the EECs are being served to the primary consumer and living systems through the food chain. Therefore, holistic approaches are vital to manage these EECs before reaching critical concentrations that may result in the drastic impacts on both living as well as non-living components of this biosphere. EECs like

flame retardants (brominated, organophosphate), perchlorate, polycyclic siloxanes, triclosan, phthalates, bisphenol-A (plasticizers), tetrabromodiphenyl ether and other organic compounds are may lead to immunological disruptions, genetic toxicity, male infertility, endocrine hormonal imbalance (estrogens, androgens, progestins), women breast cancer, ovarian tumours, thyroid mitochondrial dysfunction, neurotoxicity DNA damage resulting anatomical abnormalities and behavioral disorders (Ferreiro et al., 2020).

EECs should have been assayed for their ecotoxicological nature and detrimental effects on the biodiversity. Some of the assessed EECs include - Triclosan(methyl) accumulation in marine fish fat cells, Perchlorate inhibiting thyroid function and retarding brain development in rodents, Musk xylo a carcinogenic and neurotoxic in rats. Several prominent researchers are working in this field along with numerous other allied ones (Das et al., 2024).

Chromatography techniques specifically - Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), Supercritical-fluid chromatography, Liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectroscopy, High pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC) are the most employed instrumental analysis methods for monitoring the EECs quantitatively. Concurrently, the proliferation of emerging pollutants may be addressed by following certain mitigation strategies. Bioremediation (Membrane filtration, Osmosis), Oxidation processes (Ozone, H₂O₂), Phytoremediation (Extraction, Degradation), Sludge treatment (Nitrification) and Sorption technology (Charcoal, Silica powder) etc. are risk mitigation effective techniques for environmental EECs removal. Omics augmented biological investigations are the best methods in assaying the emerging contaminants in complex mixtures of environmental pollutants (de Oliveira et al., 2020).

Implementing the mitigation strategies is compulsory for safeguarding the global ecosystems, confirming sustainability for future generations. Raising general awareness and public concerns towards EECs are the primary components followed by scientific and industrial collaborations for their collective action. Voluntary collective efforts of all the stakeholders ranging from producers to consumers allied with regulatory bodies and academia, is the need of the hour to check the threats posed by these accumulative EECs to the biosphere.

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